
Book Review: Jackson, J. (2024). *Introducing language and intercultural communication* (3rd ed.). Routledge.

Simon McDonald¹

The University of Sydney

Jane Jackson's third edition of *Introducing Language and Intercultural Communication* underscores the critical importance of cultural understanding in effective communication, which is especially vital in today's world, where there has been an increasing tendency to resort to incendiary language against cultures and people considered different. Jackson proposes a framework that prioritises cultural sensitivity, reminding the reader that English language fluency alone is insufficient when seeking to communicate with others and that there is a need to understand and respect the cultural dimensions involved in communication.

Chapter 1 serves two primary purposes: it defines the key terms essential to understanding the rest of the book and explains why effective communication across cultures is critically important today. Jackson defines intercultural communication 'as the negotiated interpersonal interactions between individuals (or groups) with different identities (e.g. cultural, ethnic, social linguistic, regional) and varying degrees of power or status who have been socialised in different cultural and/or linguistic environments' (p. 2). She explains that the demand for skilled intercultural communicators is more pressing than ever due to the increased contact among cultures driven by technological advancements and globalisation. This need is particularly crucial to address complex global challenges—including climate change, health crises, conflicts, and the rise of extremist ideologies—in a culturally sensitive manner. The chapter ends with an important lesson on the ethical dimensions of intercultural communication.

¹ Correspondence: smcd5770@uni.sydney.edu.au; <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5624-0228>

Chapter 2 acquaints the reader with current debates about defining what culture means. Jackson discusses how children will become enculturated into the way of life of a particular society and acquire the linguistic, pragmatic and cultural norms that allow them to participate in the community. However, she recognises that the traditional perspective, which posits that individuals must learn a single set of cultural norms specific to a community, is becoming less applicable in today's dynamic, global, and multicultural context where culture is fluid and variable. The chapter then shifts to discuss an alternative perspective that suggests viewing culture through a critical lens. Similar to other constructivist thinkers, proponents of a critical approach challenge the idea of culture as a static entity inherited from one generation to the next, suggesting instead that it is actively constructed through discourse and continuously evolves according to its context (Bennett, 2020). This elevates recognition that culture does not refer to a homogeneous grouping of people with similar cultural artifacts. However, significant variation exists among individuals within any broader culture.

The topic of communication and culture is taken up in the following two chapters (Chapters 3 and 4), topics that may resonate more with those particularly interested in the linguistic aspects of culture. Communication is described as a process that is irreversible, dynamic, interactive/transactive, symbolic, intentional/unintentional, contextual, pervasive, power-infused and cultural. Jackson describes how, in the case of intercultural communication, successful interactions are highly dependent on how well interlocutors accommodate different communication styles. Some cultures favour high-context communication, where information is indirectly conveyed to engage the listener. Conversely, other cultures prefer low-context communication, which focuses on the direct exchange of ideas, information, and opinions. Furthermore, she notes the many ways communication influences non-verbal aspects (e.g. facial expression, use of space, physical appearance) and the importance of interlocutors being cognizant of how these can influence how we view others. In line with current thinking in intercultural pragmatics, effective intercultural communication is achieved when interlocutors seek to converge in their communication styles (Kecskes, 2022; Ifantidou, 2022).

The book explains how perceptions of one's own identity and that of others significantly influence intercultural communication, and at times, the dark side of identity can hinder successful interactions. Chapter 5 outlines the many dimensions of identities (e.g. social, cultural, racial and ethnic) and argues that identities are shaped by the specific context and time period and are continually

negotiated through social interactions. This definition of identity sets the stage for exploring the negative dimensions of identity in Chapter 6, where perceiving identity as static and as a homogenous property tied to specific races frequently leads to racist and xenophobic attitudes in intercultural communication contexts. At this juncture, the book presents one of the core principles of intercultural studies, ethnocentrism. An ethnocentric view sets an individual's own culture as the normative standard by which the world is best understood, and all other cultures are viewed according to this standard, which often creates negative value judgements about alternative cultural ways of knowing. Therefore, intercultural communication requires people to be mindful of their ethnocentric tendencies and refrain from snap decisions about how unfamiliar ways may be inferior to one's own culturally informed understanding of the world.

Chapter 7 explores the various forms and methods of intercultural adaptation, beginning with an overview of migratory patterns that can be either short-term or long-term. It then discusses how acculturation varies significantly based on an individual's attitude towards maintaining their home culture, adopting the new culture, or attempting to integrate both. The chapter continues by examining the experiences of students studying abroad, detailing the stages involved in adapting to a new environment. Particular focus is given to the negative and positive impacts of language and culture shock, factors that influence the severity of culture shock, and strategies that can be employed beforehand to reduce stress and frustration. This helps students prepare for and manage a disorienting experience of adjusting to a new culture.

Similar to previous chapters, Chapter 8 explores intercultural relationships by defining the nature of intercultural and interpersonal relationships. Such relationships describe the union of people across different races, ethnicities, nationalities, religions, social classes and languages. It becomes clear at this point why Jackson introduced many concepts about identity and communication styles earlier in the book, as her listing of the different facilitators and barriers to forming personal intercultural relationships draws upon this material. For example, individuals who effectively recognise the self-identities of others in a relationship tend to sustain more positive intercultural relationships. Additionally, the themes of emotional sensitivity and emotional intelligence recur throughout the chapter, adding a new layer to understanding intercultural relationships.

Jackson then addresses the problem of conflict that can disrupt relationships (Chapter 9). Differing conflict styles are a key challenge when involving more than

one culture, as cultures vary in directness and emotional expressiveness when conflict arises. Jackson discusses how conflict is often seen as an attack on a person's identity, and varying approaches to maintaining face can lead to misunderstandings. She argues that the many potential sources of conflict require that intercultural communicators enhance their understanding of culturally based conflict styles, practice mindfulness to remain aware of various emotions and thoughts, engage in self-reflection, utilise effective conflict communication skills, and maintain flexibility in their communication approaches.

While most of the book has focused on the social and relational advantages of intercultural communication, Chapter 10 shows how intercultural communication is important to creating commercially successful businesses. The chapter notes that the study of cultural differences within the business community led to the initial research on core differences between cultural groups, with many of these theories continuing to be influential today.

The concluding chapter explores the broader significance of intercultural communication by examining its relationship with overall communicative competence and its importance in ethical behaviour and global citizenship. The book highlights previous studies indicating a weak correlation between language proficiency and intercultural sensitivity, suggesting that intercultural communicative competence might be an independent construct not fully explained by traditional models of communicative competence. This is consistent with the criticism of the traditional communicative competence models proposed by Canale and Swain (1980) and Bachman (1990), which emphasise the individual. In contrast, intercultural communicative competence focuses on the speaker's ability to establish shared meaning (Yong, 2019). Jackson notes Byram's (1997) contribution to the field with the development of his model of *Intercultural Communicative Competence*. He built upon the notion of communicative competence by integrating a cultural dimension, underscoring that language learning involves more than just linguistic skills but also the development of attitudes, knowledge, critical cultural awareness, and skills in interpreting and interacting. The chapter concludes with a reminder that as global citizens, everyone needs to develop intercultural competency to respect human rights and uphold ethical responsibilities more effectively.

Jackson has intentionally crafted a book that is accessible and engaging for newcomers to intercultural communication. The readability of the book is helped by the incorporation of multiple vignettes and practical suggestions to provide

concrete examples alongside the theoretical concepts discussed. In the previous edition, she dedicated a chapter to the history of language and intercultural communication and used more technical language in the chapter titles. Jackson has since eliminated this section and revised the headings by using more accessible terms, clearly making a significant effort to make the book's content resonate with the experiences of many potential readers.

AUTHOR

Simon McDonald is currently pursuing his PhD at the University of Sydney, where his research focuses on the intercultural competence of early childhood teachers. He has a background in teaching English in Australia and South Korea, particularly in preparing students for high-stakes exams. He holds a Master of Applied Linguistics from the University of Southern Queensland, during which he successfully published his thesis on the Pearson Test of English assessing students' abilities to understand speech in noise in the *Journal of Linguistic Studies*.

REFERENCES

- Bachman, L. F. (1990). *Fundamental considerations in language testing*. Oxford University Press.
- Bennett, M. J. (2020). A constructivist approach to assessing intercultural communication competence. In G. Rings & S. Rasinger (Eds.), *Cambridge handbook of intercultural communication* (pp. 521–535). Cambridge University Press.
- Byram, M., (1997). *Teaching and assessing intercultural communicative competence*. Multilingual Matters.
- Canale, M., & Swain, M. (1980). Theoretical bases of communicative approaches to second language teaching and testing. *Applied Linguistics*, 1(1), 1–47. <https://doi.org/10.1093/applin/1.1.1>
- Ifantidou, E. (2022). Pragmatic competence. In I. Kecskes (Ed.), *The Cambridge handbook of intercultural pragmatics* (pp. 741–765). Cambridge University Press.

Kecskes, I. (2022). The rise of intercultural pragmatics. In I. Kecskes (Ed.), *The Cambridge handbook of intercultural pragmatics* (pp. 1–8). Cambridge University Press.

Young, R. (2019). Interactional competence and L2 pragmatics. In N. Taguchi (Ed.), *The Routledge handbook of second language acquisition and pragmatics*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781351164085>